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Computer Assisted Assessment in Mathematics

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ABSTRACT

New scenarios of organization of education process considerably influenced also the form of assessing knowledge and depth of understanding acquired by students. Computer Assisted Assessment (CAA) is a common term used for any form of the assessment of student learning outcomes, in which computers are used to manage or to support the assessment process. This can have several forms and follow various goals. In spite of a bias towards science and technology subjects in the use of CAA, there are increasing examples of its employment in many disciplines. Forms and variants of CAA adopted out at some European technical universities will be discussed, and analysis of results with application of CAA in Maths courses at the Mechanical Engineering Faculty of STU in Bratislava will be presented.

Conference Key Areas: Mathematics in Engineering Education, Open and Online Engineering Education

Keywords: ITC in education, on-line pedagogy, computer assisted assessment

INTRODUCTION

Computer Assisted Assessment (CAA) is assessment of student knowledge and learning outcomes utilising computers to manage or to support the process of assessing in any feasible form. Most typically this concerns a formative assessment, which is aimed to help students to discover whether they have learned what they were supposed to and to what extent they were able to grasp the knowledge. These forms of tests also provide timely feedback to educators on how to teach the subject for better students' understanding, which is particularly important in mathematics education. CAA can be also developed as summative, with a limited feedback typically being given at the end of a course and serving to grade and categorise the student's work. Occasionally, it can also be diagnostic, e.g. by testing for pre-knowledge or partial knowledge that students reached after completely covering of certain topics.

Well-written computer assisted testing is more likely to be objective testing that can be marked objectively, and thus it offers a high reliability. Great benefit is that the tests can be marked quickly and easily, and adapted to meet a wide range of learning outcomes, see in [1].

1 BASICS OF COMPUTER ASSISTED ASSESSMENTS

1.1 Advantages of CAA

CAA tests have the following potential:

- they can incorporate a wide range of media
- online assessments can be directly linked to feedback
- hints can be incorporated into test questions
- other learning activities can be assigned based on the test results
- randomized selection can be made from a larger question banks
- tests can be administrated easily
- CAA also allows better test management.

It is, however, important to consider whether CAA technology is the appropriate method of assessment in the particular subject. If it is implemented, it should probably only be used for part of the course's assessment strategies, and not as the only way of testing students' knowledge. In mathematics, particularly, a great attention has to be paid to conceptual understanding. This knowledge is not easy to be recognized and assessed by simple multiple choice tests, which are the most prevailing on-line testing forms developed usually as the first attempts when introducing CAA approach. Authors must be therefore aware of many drawbacks and disadvantages that this form of testing can bring when adopted.

1.2 Disadvantages of CAA

CAA approach can have the following limitations:

- It is usually associated with testing knowledge skills rather than conceptual understanding, because of the frequent use of multiple choice questions formatting, which is believed to test at a lower level of understanding when related to Bloom's Taxonomy
- Construction of good objective tests requires skill and practice and so it is initially rather time consuming
- Implementation of a CAA system can be quite costly
- Hardware and software must be carefully monitored to avoid any failure during examinations
- Security issues can be a problem in web based CAA
- Students are required to have adequate IT skills and experience to undertake this particular assessment type
- Assessors and invigilators need training in assessment design, IT skills and examination management
- A high level of organization is required of all parties involved in assessment (academics, support staff, computer services, and administrators).

2 RECENT DEVELOPMENT

2.1 General situation

Computer assisted assessment of higher order skills such as comprehension, application and reasoning is difficult to attain. Recent research has produced an improvement in CAA's ability to test these skills, and allowed for implementation of the suitable and sophisticated tools to be used on the Web. Areas for development include graphical hotspot questions, which involve selecting an area of the screen by moving a marker to the required position. On-line text assessment is also being developed,

with interactive respond providing hints in case of not correctly posed answers. Various learning platforms and environments with implemented tools for test development are available, both free as e.g. Khan Academy, Moodle, GeoGebra learning platform, or commercial solutions as e.g. SOWISO learning platform for Maths & Science [2], or Math-Bridge [3]. Math-Bridge is the first Pan-European e-learning platform for online bridging courses in mathematics developed as a joint effort of 9 universities from 7 countries. It allows students and teachers to work with more than thousands of mathematical learning objects (theorems, proofs, definitions, instructional examples, and interactive exercises) written in 7 languages. There are available many pre-defined courses that can be adapted to specific needs by a provided adaptive tool, and also own courses can be build.

Platform “its learning” is a learning management system that enables teachers to better facilitate instructional delivery and engage today’s “digitally” wired students. Teachers can develop lessons, distribute and collect assignments, assess quizzes and tests, or introduce on-line discussions with students to practise collaborative learning, engage students with online quizzes used for exam preparation, and use messages to keep students informed about their subjects. Platform itslearning also helps in organisational work, including improving dialogue with students and giving feedback [4].

A number of institutional Computer Based Assessment development projects (many funded by higher education initiatives) offer free or relatively inexpensive assessment tools, which do not require the purchase of costly licenses. Universities provide digital campuses to support staff and students with new digital workspace, which gives new tools and offer easy way to work online, share information and collaborate within teams. Teachers can create on-line interactive assessment tools quickly and easily without much prior knowledge about design of HTML webpages or scripting languages. Its aim is to provide online interactive tutorials and assessment environment, which should enhance the learning resources available to the student, whilst requiring a fairly minimal time investment on behalf of the tutor or course developer. Effective question design means that assessment questionnaires can test different cognitive processes (e.g. comprehension, application and evaluation) as well as the ability to recall facts. Examples are for instance E-MATHS-CH, e-learning platform for Mathematics at the University of St. Gallen [5], or M-learning Platform for Engineering Mathematics designed at the Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong, China [6].

Recently, Delft University announced their move from the Blackboard Learning Management System to a new system enabling digital examination, which is a challenge for technical university. In exams, there are a lot of mathematical graphics and most of the software doesn’t support that yet. The new learning environment also has to offer good integration with other educational software, such as software used to practice solving mathematical problems, but also with tools from student startups on the Delft campus, such as Feedbackfruits, which offers professors and students interaction possibilities inside and outside the classroom in an innovative way. University choice was D2L Brightspace, an excellent top product based on innovation and development capability. The supplier of the D2L showed it understood TU Delft’s strategic goals by offering modules the university didn’t ask for, but that fitted its educational vision [7].

2.2 Initiatives

In 2004, the SEFI Working Group on Mathematics and Engineering Education started to conduct an assessment project focused on investigation of various forms of examination and assessments used at some of the European technical universities in basic Mathematics courses. Project had three main purposes:

1. to survey the methods of assessment used in engineering mathematics across Europe;
2. to stimulate debate on appropriate and efficient methods of assessment;
3. to spread good practice in assessment.

The project findings were reported in the proceedings of the 12th SEFI MWG seminar held in Vienna in June 2004 [8]. In addition, there was a round-table discussion at the seminar on issues relating to assessment. Summary of the main ideas that delegates put forward during these discussion and the report of findings can be found at the Working Group webpage [9].

In the recent publication of updated curricula for mathematics in engineering education [10] published by SEFI, chapter 5 is devoted to assessment and its various forms. Here one can find summary of ideas presented by participants at the SEFI MWG bi-annual seminars reflecting practical experience of maths teachers at technical universities throughout the Europe with many various forms of assessments they have adopted in their pedagogical practise. Related to the innovative concept of curriculum based in developing mathematical competencies and conceptual understanding prior to calculation skills and memorised facts, ideas about how to assess competencies are presented, too. Technology supported assessments is discussed also, namely in connection to drawbacks that have to be overcome developing more sophisticated computer aided solutions. More attempts are appearing recently towards complete, computer-supported systems, the so-called Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS), where the student gets information not only about his/her errors or mistakes but also about underlying misconceptions or lack of knowledge, together with support to fill the gaps.

There are also specific problems arising with the legal certainty when IT devices are used in assessment, as computers at universities are connected to a network and to the internet. To prevent cheating the network connections and some other features of communication and usage of computer programs must be blocked, which can cause organizational problems, not speaking about possible insufficient number of available computers for large groups of students to be assessed at the same time. The need for randomization of tests questions, in order to avoid similarity that could privilege students taking test later and discriminate the last ones, is obvious. Attempts to allow students to take the on-line test out of campus or out of office hours were registered too. This approach puts more work on examiner who should avoid cheating by developing the test very carefully, cleverly posing questions focused closely on studied and tested material, as he does not know who actually took the test.

2.3 Project FutureMath

The FutureMath is project funded by the EU under the ERASMUS+ Program, with reference 2015-1-FI01-KA203-009044. It aims to respond to the requirements of modern society and to make mathematics' learning and teaching more digitalized, effective and accessible. Additionally, the aim is to explore and develop the most motivational, learner centred methods, techniques and resources for engineering mathematics learning and teaching with the help of technology. All the learning resources developed in the project will be made available for free under the idea of Open Source or Open Educational Resource (OER). The underlying notion is to support digitalization of European engineering mathematics education in a large scale. By these means, it is supposed to improve the efficiency, accessibility and quality of mathematics teaching and learning on European level which is one of the four common objectives of EU's Strategic Framework of Education and Training 2020. Additionally, as an impact of the project, improving of transversal and basic skills (ET2020), such as digital skills and mathematical skills, will be a central focus. With these actions, it is

expected not only to develop innovative learning approaches but also to enrich the teaching, support personalised learning and increase the flexibility and attractiveness. In addition to the mathematics learning platform, project aims to develop innovative pedagogical methods, techniques, materials and resources not only to teach and learn mathematics but also to assess mathematics' learning. The key approaches while planning the resources are i.e. collective thinking, collaboration and shared problem solving skills - the skills that are necessary for success in working life. Furthermore, project resources will respect individual learning solutions. Therefore, different learning types will be taken into account in the project's material production. In this way, it is also possible to decrease the inequality among different kinds of learners.

Overall, the one main objective of this project is to increase the global large-scale awareness about the possibilities ubiquitous technology offers for mathematics learning throughout MLP. Global aim is to make mathematics learning more motivational, interesting and to increase accessibility and the alternative modern methods for mathematics learning.

The project consortium consists of 4 partners, TAMK – Tampere University of Applied Sciences, Finland, TUCEB – Technical University of Civil Engineering Bucharest, Romania, STUBA – Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Slovakia, and UPM – Technical University of Madrid, Spain, working in two teams: team mathematics and team technology. TAMK, TUCEB and STUBA mostly participate in mathematics team and UPM and TAMK are engaged also in technology team. These two teams closely cooperate, while team mathematics is mostly responsible about the developments related to the mathematics (assessment, pedagogy, production of learning resources etc.), whereas team technology is responsible for the technical innovation and implementations. The project coordinator is TAMK [11]. Mathematical learning platform has been opened recently, with innovative learning materials developed for general usage and share for all interested party.

3 ASSESSMENT STRATEGIES AT STU IN BRATISLAVA

3.1 Blended solution

Mathematics educators at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Slovakia, introduced (several years ago) blended system of assessment of faculty students in basic mathematics courses Mathematics I and Mathematics II for bachelor study programmes scheduled in the first two semesters of the first year. The idea of implementing partially also computer assessment solutions originated in connection to lack of academic staff with overwhelming duties to examine great groups of university freshmen. Facing the consequences of overall development with decreasing mathematical competencies of secondary school graduates arriving to university study, specific pre-tests had to be developed, in order to assess level of basic maths knowledge. Based on test results students were advised to take additional exercises in maths, in both semesters, to support their needs in reaching the standard level of necessary knowledge for their successful performance in basic courses Mathematics I and II. E-learning platform with various digital and interactive learning materials was provided in Slovak to support students' needs.

Final formative assessments for passing additional maths classes were designed as classical multiple choice tests in written form. Results were compared with the pre-tests with visible knowledge gain for almost all students. Simultaneously to additional classes students attended normal classes of Mathematics I (first semester) and Mathematics II (second semester). They had to pass 2 tests during each semester. First test was a classical written test, the second test was performed as CAA in

computer laboratory. Students had to prove their knowledge and abilities to solve few more difficult problems using computer algebra system available at university, namely Wolfram Mathematica. In spite of the fact that our students worked in computer laboratory with the Mathematica system throughout the whole semester, computer assisted tests displayed considerably worse results than the traditional ones. Analyses of problems that students encountered when enrolled in the CAA, we came to the following conclusions:

- In classical written tests students concentrate entirely on the essential mathematical problem they solve / in computer assisted tests, concentration of attendees has to be split between mastering operations on the digital media first, and solving initial mathematical problem itself, that is at the second place.
- Writing of maths symbols in the classical written tests is much easier and more natural for students then scripting in the symbolic language of used CAS, which leads to more time wasted on scripting than on solving during the testing period.
- Some traditional calculation skills are no more necessary when using CAA.
- Many partial problems hidden in and necessary in step by step calculations that are actually giving the evidence of a profound mastering of the tested mathematical task can be solved by CAS without understanding, which is leading to weak surface knowledge not sufficient for sustainable conceptual understanding in mathematics.
- Solving complex problems, which is often very time consuming, is not possible in traditional way of testing / CAA becomes more complex and complicated, as chosen problems are often more difficult than in the traditional testing scenarios.
- Students rely on CAS provided offerings and try to solve given problems automatically, without proper reasoning and using knowledge they should acquire from the course, which results in more frequent occurrence of not-correct solutions caused by improper interpretation of the problem.
- Good students performed better in CAA when they were allowed to use CAS, as they could concentrate more on the solution strategies than on the manual calculations necessary to perform the test tasks/ weaker students had more problems in CAA than in classical testing, as they were not able to cope with two different tasks – maths problem and computer mastering, at once.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Computer assisted assessment in mathematics is a complex issue that is still not well analysed due to various reasons. Keeping in mind the fact of the ongoing lack of suitable tools for easy management of mathematical formulas communicated via ICT devices, concentration of test attendees will be inevitably disturbed by the double burden of solving and scripting all solution steps. On the other hand, some parts of the solution might be skipped or solved by used CAS, which can easily lead to false understanding of solved mathematical tasks and often also to incorrect solutions caused by misunderstanding and weak surface knowledge. Further decrease of mathematical skills has been registered in connection to usage of digital technologies, both in learning-teaching and in assessment. Anyhow, all consequences and real impact of digitalised education on mathematical abilities, calculation skills and conceptual understanding of students were not expected and absolutely not envisaged. In some situations the results of digital technologies introduction are far from promising assumptions of great improvements in delivery of mathematics courses, at technical universities in particular. Recently, students prefer face-to-face consultations and direct contact with teachers during preparation for exams to self-study and usage of available e-learning resource and interactive on-line materials.

Positive aspects of CAA introduction can be seen mainly in gained time that can be saved when assessing large groups of students using computer assisted testing. Better performing students are thus equipped with powerful tools enabling them to concentrate more on real and therefore more complex mathematical problems and their solutions than on tedious manual calculations. On the other hand, for some of the weaker students just the opposite might be true. They were able to solve more complex problems due to availability of CAS powerful tools for performing calculation of merely trivial tasks as these could cause fatal problems. Therefore, students were able to deal with more complicated mathematics without its deep understanding.

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